

DOMINANT LEADERSHIP STYLE OF SCHOOL PRINCIPALS AND THEIR ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE

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Abstract: This study aimed to determine school principals' dominant leadership style and organizational environment in Apopong District. The analysis used a descriptive research method. A survey questionnaire was used to collect data. Frequency and percentage were used to treat the data gathered. Results showed the dominant leadership style of the school principals of New Society Central Elementary School, Lanton Elementary School, GSC Elementary School for Arts and Lozano Elementary School was democratic, Paopao Elementary School principal was laissez-faire and Sinawal Elementary School's principal, was autocratic. Consequently, the organizational climate of each school in Apopong District was supportive. The organizational climate when analyzed according to the school principal's dominant leadership styles was supportive. Nevertheless, the school principals' leadership style can vary wherein teachers faced the same organizational environment. The implication of this study highlights the significant role of the dominant leadership style of school principals in shaping the organizational climate, emphasizing the need for effective leadership development programs and strategies that promote a positive and supportive work environment within educational institutions.

Keywords: Educational management, teachers, dominant leadership style, organizational climate, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Leadership style and organizational climate are interdependent. Both may impact one another's ability to achieve positive results. Common to all schools is the presence of a principal who works through a group or groups to achieve organizational goals. To arrive at these goals, the school head adopts one leadership style or another. Whatever leadership style is adopted will determine the sort of cooperation and relationship that will exist between the principal and her subordinates.

A principal who does not have the power within cannot gain respect. Respect is essential to lasting leadership. Leaders deserve respect by making sound decisions, admitting their mistakes, and putting what is paramount for their allies and the organization ahead of their agenda. A leader's good character builds trust among his/her followers. However, when he/she breaks the confidence, he/she forfeits his/her ability to lead. No leader can break trust with his/her people and expect to keep the same level of influence with them. Trust is the foundation of leadership. Vision is everything for a leader. It is utterly indispensable because vision leads the leader; it paints the target, sparks, fuels the fire within, and draws him forward.

One of the most worthy advantages of vision was, it acts as a magnet—attracting, challenging, and uniting people. The significant the insight, the more it has the potential to persuade. The more challenging the imagination is, the harder the participants fight to achieve it (Gibson, 2008).

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Motivation, performance, and job satisfaction may be affected by the workplace by establishing the perceptions of workers regarding the effects of various behavior. Employees expect positive benefits, approvals, and discontent from their knowledge of the environment of the company. A sound operating environment is a long-term proposal. Managers ought to take an opportunistic approach to the working world, which means that they take an institutional asset the long view of the environment. Unwise discipline and placing pressure on individuals can lead to better outcomes temporarily. An organization like this will inevitably suffer from depleted resources (Velasky and Owens, 2011).

The center of teamwork is confidence. It is fundamental to human interactions inside and outside the organization. Leaders cannot lead without confidence. Without reliance, they cannot get unusual things done. Others fail to become leaders precisely because they were unable to trust others' words and work. They both end up doing all the effort themselves and supervise work so strictly that they become over-controlling. Their evident lack of belief in others results in others' lack of assurance in them (Manning and Curtis, 2009).

Teachers from different schools had varied experiences from different school heads' leadership styles that somehow affect the school's organizational climate. Teachers compare their school heads to the other school heads based on what they have observed and experienced. In effect, faction and conflicts exist when one was given the favor and recognition for a job well done, and with the same effort, a reprimand was for others.

Violating rules as set forth was acceptable if somebody belongs to his or her shield and receiving a memorandum for those who were not with a requirement of a written reply within 72 hours or less.

Nowadays, the measurement of leadership effectiveness includes the fact that at any time, any leader will be perceived differently by his or her subordinates. Some will welcome a new approach, while others will cling to the past. Some want decisiveness, while others need collaboration because leadership is the foremost predictor of teachers' satisfaction with school-based phenomena such as supervision, communication, and decision making.

The researcher conducted this research to find out the dominant leadership style of the principals of Apopong District, and so as with the organizational climate, it has under their leadership.

This study determined the dominant leadership style of school principals in Apopong District and their organizational climate.

Specifically, this study was pursued to discover answers to the following:

1. What is the dominant leadership style of principals in Apopong District?
2. What is the organizational climate of schools in Apopong District?
3. What is the organizational climate of schools in Apopong District when analyzed according to principals' leadership style?

The cornerstone of this research was the Situational Leadership Theory of Paul Hersey and Ken Blanchard (late 1970s/early 1980s). There was no single "best style of leadership, the basic underpinning of this theory. Effective leadership is task-relevant, and those who adapt their management to the creation of the distinct or set to direct or influence are the most efficient leaders. Effective leadership varies, not only with the individual or community being governed but also with the mission, job, or role being realized.

Another theory on which this study was anchored is the Field Theory by Kurt Lewin (1940). A person's life is made up of several diverse spaces, according to field theory. Forces are pushing a person toward his/her goal. One must go through to reach his/her plan, and go through different extent. The domain to get there may be diverse, but individuals may have the same goal.

One's field may be accustomed to attaining the utmost in life. Removing some extent and some were supplementary, all depending on definite actions in a person's lifetime.

Field theory also includes the impression that every person has unlike proficiencies in a given condition. Two people's familiarity with an occurrence will not be alike. Still, there will be some differences that lead to the idea that no two

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involvements are the same for a person either, as the dynamic field is continually changing. The self-motivated arena is like a river, continuously streaming while changing a little.

Another piece of field theory views the impression that no part of a person's arena as being senseless. Each part of an entire field beholds as having possible meaning and importance. It should still be accounted for irrespective of how insignificant or non-important the part of the field may seem.

The Significance of the Study

This study was set about with the optimism that the findings proved helpful to the following:

Schools of Apopong District. The study will provide the school with essential information on how the teachers observe the leadership style of their school principals within the school organizational structure.

School Principals of Apopong District. This study could serve as a medium towards self-improvement and would enable them to create a school atmosphere that is susceptible to every individual under their supervision.

Teachers. It may help them to broaden their minds in understanding and adopting the different leadership styles of their school heads and encourage them to establish a harmonious superior-subordinate relationship.

Researcher. She will gain in detail the understanding and skills in doing research; thus, nurturing the values of realistic outlook, serenity, discipline, systematic, humbleness, and initiative.

Future researchers. This study may provide them additional information and related studies to guide them in doing their research.

To understand the languages frequently used in this study, the researcher conceptually and operationally defined the following: Dominant Leadership Style. The term refers to the prevailing or common styles of providing direction, implementing plans, and motivating people who were given power and authority to run an organization. Operationally, it refers to the most common leadership styles observed in the schools of Apopong District whether autocratic, where the leader makes all the resolutions and passes the directives to subordinates under close supervision, democratic, where the leader involves the populaces in the decision-making or laissez-faire, where the leader is "hands-off" and allow group members to make the resolutions. Organizational Climate. The term refers to a generalized perception that people employ in thinking about and describing the organizations where they work. Operationally, it refers to the present working environment that the school personnel had experienced, whether enlightened, shows a rational, modern, well-informed outlook and spiritually aware, supportive, provide encouragement or emotional help, impoverished, involves a low level of concern for people and the organization's productivity, or exploitive, uses threats, fear, and punishment to motivate their subordinates.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The following related literatures are based on different researches and are found to have similarities and have bearing born on leadership styles and organizational climate.

Leadership Styles

A leadership style is a leader's style of imparting way, implementing plans, and encouraging people. There are diverse leadership styles exhibited by leaders in the political, business, or other fields. There are three main types of leadership: 1) autocratic; strong, directing and controlling acts to implement rules and regulations; 2) democratic; collaborative, mutual, and cooperative actions of followers; and 3) laissez-faire; it implies that the leader does not want to take responsibility as a leader (Apura, 2012).

Many leaders tend to fit into and follow one of the leadership styles. Now for the big revelation, a good leader uses all three approaches, depending on the situation. A successful leader does it all (Da Costa, 2012).

Whether or not managers choose among leadership styles in different situations can become a great challenge. The issue is essential because it can affect a wide range of management selection, placement, and promotion activities. If managers are versatile in leadership style or prepared to vary their style, they are likely to be useful in various leadership situations. On the other hand, managers are relatively inflexible in leadership style, then they only perform successfully in conditions that

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better fit their style. Such inflexibility would not hamper the careers of managers but would also complicate the organization's task of filling its management positions (Angeles, 2010).

Leadership consists of these parts. The first is to have a vision or an objective or a goal. The second is to articulate that goal to other members of the team and to obtain their commitment to that objective. Third, designing and executing a strategy to achieve that aim. Not everyone is born or taught to be a leader, but specific skills and attitudes enable us to lead, whether directly or from the side. Good leadership is the effect of the careful application of these skills (Desamito, 2010).

A leader can take some different approaches to leadership and managing an organization. A leader's style of giving instruction, setting approach, and encouraging people is the product of their behavior, values, preparation, and practice. For example, a leader with an easygoing temperament may lead with a less proper style that encourages sovereignty and inventiveness (McCarthy, 2015).

Newstrom and Davis (1993) (as cited by Clark, 2014) stated that leadership style implements plans, the manner and approach of providing direction, and encouraging people. As perceived by the employees, it contains the entire pattern of explicit and implicit actions performed by their leader.

They added that Kurt Lewin conducted the first major leadership style analysis in 1939, leading a group of researchers to define various leadership styles. The three key leadership styles were developed in this early study. They remained very influential: (1) authoritarian or autocratic tells his or her staff what to do and how to do it without receiving their advice, (2) participatory or democratic includes one or more staff in the decision-making process, but the leader usually retains the final decision-making authority, and (3) delegate or laissez-fair allows were the leader, nevertheless, remains responsible for decisions taken.

If coordinated with the situation's necessities and used by a trained leader who can adopt a skillful approach, each leadership style can be useful. The most potent leaders are proficient at numerous techniques and gifted to select the one most probable to assist the organization to realize its objectives (McCarthy, 2015).

Leadership style depends on the leader's and the organization's conception of what leadership is and the leader's choice of leadership methods. Depending on how those fit together, a leader might adopt one of the various methods, each replicated in how the organization functions and how its staff members relate to one another. Specific possibilities include: (1) autocratic, entirely in control, making all decisions himself, (2) managerial, apprehensive with the smooth process, rather than the goals and efficiency of the organization, (3) democratic, referring with others, encouraging impartiality within the organization, but making concluding decisions herself, and (4) collaborative, sharing leadership, involving others in all significant pronouncements, disseminating ownership of the organization.

The alternative way of viewing leadership is to classify it as either transactional (based on dealings such as compensate in return for work) or transformational (based on soliciting people in quest of a vision pronounced by the leader, but built on their requirements and ambitions, which purposes an actual change). Merging this opinion with that grounded on the four styles make it simple to comprehend how leaders function and creative decisions. It also makes explicit that diverse types may be suitable for different resolutions. Many leaders move back and forth among numerous in a day, even if there is one characterizing them (Rabinowitz, 2014).

Leadership techniques can't be tried on like so many costumes to perceive what it fits. They should be tailored to the local needs of the situation, the specific needs of the people involved and the precise challenges facing the organization (Jones, 2015).

The leadership approach is how a leader realizes his purposes. It can have philosophical possessions in an organization and its staff members and can regulate whether the organization is active or not (McCarthy, 2015).

A noble leader uses all three styles, depending on what forces are between the cohorts, the forerunner, and the condition (Clark, 2014).

Though good leaders utilize all three styles, with one of them usually dominant, bad leaders tend to stick with the one type, typically autocratic (Rabinowitz, 2014).

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He further emphasized that one can choose and develop leadership styles and skills by assessing one's inclinations and abilities, considering the group's necessities or ingenuity, discerning other leaders and finding a counselor, believing in oneself, and being set to transformation.

Although a suitable leadership style depends on the condition, three factors influence which leadership style to use.

First, the superior's training. What character, information, morals, beliefs, and capabilities does the superior have? Second, the employees being supervised. Employees are person with unlike temperaments and upbringings; leadership style superior's routine will diverge depending upon the distinct employee and what he or she will respond best. Third, the organization, the traditions, values, philosophy, and concerns of the organization will influence how superior acts.

Autocratic (Authoritarian) Leadership Style

The Authoritarian Leadership Style is described by a leader who makes the entire decision and passes directives to subordinates who are likely to carry these out under very close direction. Any subordinates trying to interrogate the directive given is discouraged. There is slight or no chance for subordinates to develop resourcefulness and creativeness through such means as punishment, reward, arbitrary rules, and task orientation control employee's behavior (Brennen, 2011).

Authoritarian (Autocratic), this is the simplest. One can decide; it is someone's way or the high way of discussion (Da Costa, 2012).

An autocratic leadership style has the following characteristics: 1) Leader seeks to make as many decisions as possible. 2) Leader aims to have the most authority and control in decision making. 3) Leader seeks to retain responsibility rather than utilize the entire delegation. 4) Consultation with other colleagues is minimal, and decision making becomes a solitary process. 5) Leaders are less concerned with investing in their leadership development and prefer to work on the task at hand (Apura, 2012).

Leaders are telling their employees what they want to do and how they want it accomplished without listening to the advice of their followers. This style may be appropriate when used when an individual has all the information to solve the problem, one has a limited time, and employees are well motivated (Clark, 2014).

He posited that some people tend to think of this style as a vehicle for yelling, demeaning language, and leading by threats. That is not the authoritarian style; instead, it is an offensive, unethical style called "bossing people around." It has no room in a leader's repertoire.

The autocratic leader used commands on the subordinates and expects compliance from them. He or she is dogmatic, positive, and uses rewards and punishment to an exact agreement (Kendra, 2009).

She added that the autocratic leader takes decisions without consulting others. In Lewin's experiments, he establishes that this triggered the most level of dissatisfaction. An autocratic leadership works once there is no need to contribute to the conclusion, when the decision would not change due to information, and when people's enthusiasm for subsequent actions would not affect whether they were tangled in decision-making.

The authoritarian leadership style assumes that the leader knows everything and knows what is best for the organization. Employees are ignorant, lazy. They lack determination, loathing responsibility, and prefer control. Employees cannot be relied upon to do what is right for the organization. Limitless authority is thus indeed bestowed on the leader (Paster, 2013).

Under the autocratic leadership style unifies policymaking power in the leader. Leaders do not amuse any proposals or initiatives from subordinates. Strict supervision is useful for quick decision making but is generally not successful in fostering employee engagement or maintaining worker satisfaction (McCarthy, 2015).

An autocratic leadership style offers several advantages despite the many criticisms accorded to these styles. The benefits offered by the Autocratic Style included the following: a.) Faster decision making. When only one person makes decisions with minimal consultation, decisions are made quicker and allow the management team to respond to changes more quickly. b.) A more productive group while the leader is watching. It is ideal for poorly motivated employees who have little concern interest in their performance. c.) Reduced stress due to increase control. The manager ultimately has personal and legal responsibility for a project. Thus, it will comfort them and reduce their stress levels to know that they have control over

their fate. d) Improved logistics of operations. Having one leader with significant involvement in many areas makes it more likely to mark that problems in advance and deadlines are met (Apura, 2012).

Authoritarian leaders can be intimidating, bragging, and selfish. Despite their weaknesses, the autocratic leadership style is well suited for particular environments such as the military, a prison, and the like. This style would also be suitable for leading beginning teachers in the school situation because they are inexperienced and tend to need more direction.

On rare occasions, only use the authoritarian style. On the contrary, if somebody has the time and wants to gain more motivation and commitment from employees, they should practice the participative style (Clark, 2014).

Democratic (Participative) Leadership Style

Another leadership style practiced is democracy—commonly called participative leadership. Here, the democratic leader shares power, authority, and responsibility to his followers or his subordinates. Further, he encourages, promotes, and practices participation in problem-solving and decision-making, and general activities of the group. The democratic style would seem to be the best because of its ability to transform leaders and followers into a cohesive and cooperative group, whose collective performance results in improved quality and quantity of work (Angeles, 2010).

In the democratic style, the leader includes the individuals in the decision-making. However, the procedure for the final decision may differ from the leader having the final say to them smoothing agreement in the group (Brennen, 2011).

He further added that democratic decision-making is usually appreciated by the people, mainly if used to arbitrary decisions with which they disagreed. It can be problematic when there is an extensive range of ideas, and there is no sturdy method of attaining a reasonable final decision.

Participative (Democratic) is where you allow your subordinates to have a say in what happens. It works well in promoting a sense of team and helping employees gain their confidence and value their opinion while asking for their input, reserve the right of the final decision for oneself (Da Costa, 2012).

In a participative or democratic style of leadership, the leader shares the decision-making authority with group members. Participative leadership can benefit employees who feel more invested in conclusions and more dedicated to the adoptions because they have a say in them. This approach values the viewpoints and welfares of individual group members while also subsidizing team unity (McCarthy, 2015).

Democratic governance involves the leader, including one or more employees in the decision-making process. However, the leader still possesses the final decision-making authority. This style is not an indication of feebleness but a sign of strength that the employees will respect their leader (Clark, 2014).

He further emphasized that using this style as a leader, have part of the data, and employees have other portions. A leader is not anticipated to know everything—this is why one employs experienced and trained people. Hence, using this style is of the common advantage as it allows them to become part of the team and make better decisions.

In democratic or participative leadership, the members are an integral part of the decision-making process. They are encouraged to share their thoughts. This leadership style involves allowing members of the group to share and contribute ideas (Apura, 2012).

She added that the style has the following characteristics: a) seeks consultation on all significant issues and decision, b) effectively delegates tasks to subordinates and give them full control and responsibility for those tasks, c) welcomes feedback on the results of initiative and work environment heartens others to become leaders and be involved in leadership growth.

Democratic leadership style characterizes a structured but cooperative approach to decision-making. It focuses on sensitivity to the people in the organization and group relationships. This kind of leadership style adopts professional aptitude. Supervision is negligible as individuals take accountability for their conduct. Subordinates are fortified to express their notions and make proposals. However, collective decisions are not likely to happen in all aspects of organizational operations. Democratic leaders sell ideas. They tend to have warmth, confidence, and a friendly personality (Crowther, 2009).

The democratic leadership style of leadership is beneficial because it will result in: a) positive work environment. A culture where junior employees are given a fair amount of responsibility and are allowed to challenge themselves is where employees are more enthused about working and enjoying what they do. b) successful wits. The procedure of discussion and response naturally results in better decision-making and more effective operations. c) Creative thinking. The free flow of ideas and a positive work environment is the perfect catalyst for creative thinking. d) The reduction of friction and office politics. By allowing employees to use their ideas and, even more importantly—gain credit for them, leaders are neatly reducing the number of tension employees (Apura, 2012).

Moreover, she added that the democratic style is most effective when the leader: a) desires to keep employees knowledgeable about matters that distress them, b) wants staffs to share in decision making and problem-solving duties, c) wants to make available opportunities for employees to develop a high sense of personal development and job gratification, d) has or multifaceted problem that requires lots of effort to solve, e) modifies or solves problems that upset employees or groups of employees, and f) wants to reassure team building and participation.

Although they already knew the answer, soliciting suggestions and opinions provides more room for creativity than insularity. According to Katherine Phillips, so as one thinks about diversity and its effects in organizations during this tough economic time, he recognizes that the most robust practical value is that it challenges everyone in an organization. We are more thoughtful, and we understand and utilize more of the information that we have at our disposal when diversity is present. That is, diversity's real value (Clark, 2014).

The style of leadership that is participatory is an effective way of convening the school head and the teachers together on problems and decisions to work hand in hand as a team. A participative school administrator takes responsibility for the operation of the school. Still, he shares the operating responsibility with those who perform different tasks by giving them trust and confidence. Hence, the teacher feels a sense of involvement in the schools' goals and targets (Bona, 2010).

Democratic leadership can generate high quality and aggregate work for long periods: numerous employees like the trust they obtain an answer with support, team spirit, and high morale (Angeles, 2010).

However, do not use democratic leadership when: a.) there is not enough time to get everyone's input, b.) the organization cannot afford mistakes, c.) the superior feel threatened by this type of leadership, and d.) employee's safety is a critical concern (Bona, 2010).

Democratic leadership has some potential downsides though described as the most effective leadership style. In circumstances where duties are uncertain or time is of the principle, democratic leadership can lead to communication disappointments and undone projects. In some circumstances, colleagues, might not have been capable of making excellent contributions to the decision-making process (Apura, 2012).

Laissez-faire (Delegative) Leadership Style

The laissez-faire leadership style is quite the opposite of the authoritarian style. There is a lack of any true leadership, and everyone is free to do as it satisfies. Typically, with no goals or guidance, there is a state of misperception and lack of self-reliance in leadership. Often, to finish the mission at hand, employees doubted their ability. Consequently, the yield is usually very stumpy (Kendra, 2009).

Delegative (Laissez-Faire) is where you delegate or put someone else in charge of a particular project or task. It instills confidence in the employees and allows them to learn how to be a leader themselves (Da Costa, 2012).

Laissez-faire leadership, also known as free reign leadership, is a leadership style in which leaders accommodate and let group members make the choices. The manager comes up with little or no direction and gives employees as much autonomy as likely. Giving all rights or power to the employees, and they govern objectives, make conclusions, and decide problems on their own (Apura, 2012).

In this style, the leader consents the employees to create the assessments. However, the leader is still accountable for making decisions. When workers can evaluate the situation and determine what to do and how to use it (Clark, 2014).

He added that this is not a style to use to blame others when things go wrong but a style to be used when one fully trust and have confidence in the people under your supervision.

A person may be in a headship position without providing flawless direction, sending off the group to decide its path in achieving aims. Subordinates are given a free hand in determining their policies and techniques. Laissez-faire is most operative when workers have the skills to work autonomously, self-motivated, and will be held accountable for results (McCarthy, 2015).

Moreover, laissez-faire leadership characterizes very slight assistance from leaders, complete freedom for followers to make decisions, leaders provide the devise and means needed, group members are anticipated to solve the problem on their own (Apura, 2012).

This leadership style is operational when: a.) employees are highly skilled, experienced, and educated, b.) employees have pleasure in their work and the determination to do it successfully on their own, c.) outside experts, such as staff specialist or consultants, are being used, and employees are trustworthy and experienced.

Furthermore, do not use this style if it makes employees feel unconfident at a manager's inaccessibility. The manager cannot be responsible for regular feedback to let employees know how beautiful they are doing. Managers cannot express appreciation to employees for good work, and the manager does not understand his/her responsibilities and is hoping that employees can cover for him or her (Kendra, 2009).

Although this leadership style is not typically encouraged, it has its abode with extremely driven persons and can work entirely on their preference. This type of leadership style could also be suitable when there is nothing substantial at stake. For example, if teachers desired to celebrate, then a laissez-faire style would be the most appropriate (Brennen, 2011).

The laissez-faire style minimizes the leader's participation in decision-making, hence consenting people to sort their own choices, although they may still be liable for the aftermath. Laissez-faire functions best when people are adept and enthused in constructing their own decisions. There are no central coordination requirements, such as sharing resources across a range of different people and groups.

Organizational Climate

School organizational climate refers to teachers' perception of the school's general work environment, formal organization, participant personalities, and organization development effect.

It is internal characteristics that distinguish one school from another, influencing each school's members' actions.

The organizational atmosphere is the social environment in which workers of organization work. It may refer to the department's environment, major corporate units such as a branch plant, or a whole organization. Climate can't be seen or touched; it's there. Like room air, it covers and influences everything that happens in an organization. In turn, almost anything in an organization impacts the environment. It's a dynamic concept (Valesky et al., 2011).

The organizational environment is focused on specific observations. It is often characterized as the normal behavioral arrangements, outlooks, and emotional state that depict life in an organization and refers to current circumstances in an organization and linkages between working groups' performance. Climate, therefore, is usually more easily manipulated by management to directly affect the behavior of employees (Griffin and Moorhead, 2012).

Organizational climate, while defined inversely by many academics and scholars, usually refers to the amount to which a group emphasizes and stresses: novelty; suppleness, gratitude, and appreciation; concern for employee security; learning and growth; nationality and morals; excellent performance; engrossment and authorization and leadership (Slocum, 2009).

Allen (2003) (as cited by Cayubin, 2012) stated that leadership dramatically influences the organizational climate.

Organizational climate, as manifested in a variety of human resource executives, is an imperative judge of structural realization. Plentiful studies have found positive dealings between constructive organizational environments and various organizational attainment actions, most remarkably for metrics such as transactions, staff preservation, customer gratification, and cost-effectiveness (Woodman, 2009).

Forehand et. al., (1964) (as cited by Cayubin, 2012) stated that an organizational climate is a condition of an institution perceived by the workers. It is the worker's opinion of the worksite and the teacher's experience of the teaching-learning environment.

Climate was initially regarded as a universal notion to express the continuing eminence of structural life. Renato Taguiri (1968) noted that "a particular alignment of persistent features of the ecosystem, ambiance, social system, and ethos would create a climate, as much as a precise pattern of personal individualities establishes a personality."

B. H. Gilmer (1966) defines organizational climate as "those individualities that discriminate the association from other groups and that affect the behavior of societies in the organizations." George Litwin and Robert Stringer introduced perception into their definition of climate: "a convention of quantifiable assets of the work background based on the cooperative insights of the people who animate and labor in the setting and established to impact their behavior."

Over the years, there is some agreement on the rudimentary properties of organizational climate; Marshall Poole (1985) condenses the agreement as follows: (a) Organizational climate is apprehensive with large units; it exemplifies properties of a whole organization or main subdivision of units, (b) Organizational climate labels an entity of organization rather than appraises it or indicates expressive reactions to it, (c) Organizational climate ascends from repetitive organizational practices that are significant to the body and its affiliates, and (d) Organizational climate stimulates members' manners and outlooks (Hoy et al., 2013).

Climate can affect enthusiasm, enactment, and job fulfillment. It does this by creating employee's expectations about what consequences will follow from different actions. Employees expect sure rewards, satisfaction, and frustration by their perception of the organization's climate. A sound climate is a long-run scheme. Managers need to yield assets methodology to the environment, meaning that they take the long view of climate as an organizational asset. Unwise discipline and putting pressure on people may not result in better performance, but at the cost of the acquisition called climate. Such an organization eventually will suffer from depleted assets (Velasky et al., 2011).

He added that organizations, like fingerprints and snowflakes, are always exceptional. Each has its principles, civilizations, and lines of action, which, in his or her full amount, organize its climate. Some organizations are bustling and efficient, supplementary is easygoing.

Some are fairly human; others are stiff and cold. An organization inclines to fascinate and preserve people who fit its climate so that each pattern perpetuates to some extent. Just as people may choose to move to a definite geographic climate of the sea, mountain, or desert, they also will choose the organizational climate they prefer.

Das (2012) (as cited by Cayubin, 2012) stated that it has a significant impact on workforce performance and organizational outcomes. Workplace climate helps in boosting employees to perform their level best.

The relationship between the individuals or groups communicating and the type of climate they create during their communication affects how messages are received. The sender's and receiver's trust influence over each other, the sender's aspirations regarding upward mobility in the organization, and norms and sanctions of the group to which the sender and receiver belong influence the quality of communication. When people confide in each other, their communication leans towards being more truthful and expose; on the contrary, when they distrust each other, they are more likely to be secretive or hesitant to speak openly. That is why it is imperative for school administrators to engender trust in their colleagues if they expect to be effective (Palestini, 2011).

Harmony or a healthy superior-subordinate relationship can work wonders, especially in attaining common goals and objectives.

On the contrary, where there is no harmony, there will be chaos and confusion; there will be no definite direction, and there will never be sure solutions to problems. There can only be harmony between teachers, and they're superior if and when the latter exhibits qualities and idiosyncrasies that jibes with what the former expects from him (Bautista, 2011).

Participation is incidental when the elements such as mental and emotional involvement, motivation to contribute, and acceptance of responsibility among the school teachers are not present. The mental and emotional involvement of the teachers is where the entire self is involved, not only his skills and talents. When the teachers participate, they are not the only task involved, but also ego-involved. Participation motivates teachers to accept responsibility in their group tasks to get the job done to feel responsible (Bona, 2010).

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The concepts of leadership, employee engrossment, organizational climate, and job satisfaction are very indispensable factors in the life and existence of any organization. An organization's presence rests on the behavior and boldness of its labor force towards their given duties and the capacities of leaders to succeed and recollect its prolific workers. An organization may have ample planning, unifying, and guiding procedure, but may not endure because of poor governance.

Exploitive

Exploitive tends to use threats, fear, and punishment to motivate their subordinates. Superior at the top of the hierarchy makes all of the decisions and is customarily unmindful of the problems confronted by those in the lower levels of the organization. Decisions are enforced on subordinates, and motivation is categorized by intimidations. The instructions issued from the top make up the goals for the organization. As a consequence, labor has a tendency to be unsympathetic towards organizational objectives and can require actions contrary to those goals (Cayubin, 2012).

Exploitative leadership, with virtually no involvement by participants, is tyrannical and graded. Leaders make choices, and without inquiry, members are required to comply. Leaders show little self-reliance or trust in others, and members do not feel permitted to discuss job-related problems with leaders. In an unrestricted social and economic order, oppressive organizations seldom endure because people avoid them as much as possible. They exist; they are characterized by the absence of faithfulness and intermittent financial disasters (Manning et al., 2012).

In an exploitive system, dependents follow the pronouncements of their leaders with little or no input. Loathing to negative concerns and disciplinary measures are the main rousing factor. An abusive system falls under the authoritarian leadership style by Lewin, but it is stereotypically an adverse working milieu (Shead, 2015).

He added that an exploitive system typically has very underprivileged disclosure and a minimal combination of work. Orders derive from the person in charge and give it to the people doing the job, but there is very little response going up the command series. It means that leadership is functional without the advantage of knowing what is happening in the work course.

An exploitive climate is where the leader has a truncated concern for people and uses such methods as pressures and other fear-based methods to succeed in conformity. Communication is almost entirely downward and ignores the psychologically distant concerns of people (Straker, 2015).

Impoverished

Impoverished organizational climate deprives strength, vitality, and creativeness (Cayubin, 2012).

Impoverished leadership makes some attempts to escape being entirely monocratic. Power remains at the top but gives members random opportunities for partaking in the decision-making process. Disadvantaged organizations fall into two categories that determine their relative success. Successful impoverished organizations are benevolent autocrats in which leaders have a genuine concern for the welfare of members. Declining disadvantaged organizations are dictatorships that do not deliberate the interests or ideas of members. Through autocratic, some organizations had benevolent leaders who achieve good results. Then, as time permits and new leaders undertake authority, the authoritarian leadership style is upheld, but magnanimity is not, and the organization fails (Manning et al., 2012).

An impoverished leadership style comprises a low level of worry for people and the administration's productivity. This sort of leader does the minimum necessary to maintain her position, but no more. For example, an impoverished leader of a construction company might assign workers jobs without considering their abilities and experience and might ignore productivity and quality-control problems (Mack, 2014).

The impoverished leader has the slightest apprehension for people and production. This leader has no means of getting work done, nor is the working climate maintaining or retaining workers. The low interest of this leader in the job and work environment results in unsystematic work, discontented workers, and a lack of coherence (Kadian-Baumeyer, 2014).

Supportive

A positive community gives motivation or emotional support (Cayubin, 2012).

Supportive leadership reflects a great organization of members' curiosity and assurance. Authority resides in leadership, but in the organization, there is precise coordination and engagement. People know the organization's goals and ensure they prevail. Associates feel unregulated to work-related issues with leaders. This leadership structure needs a broad involvement of stakeholders and engagement in decision-making (Manning et al., 2012).

Supervisors do not necessarily give tasks in a constructive organizational environment, gathering results only. Instead, they work side by side with employee tasks to advance skills and talent before the managers have to think about doing a job thoroughly and adequately empowering the subordinates in a particular mission (Lacoma, 2014).

Supportive leadership helps to build and sustain efficient interpersonal relationships. A manager who is compassionate and accommodating to individuals is more likely to achieve their relation and loyalty. The passionate connections formed to make it easier for individuals on whom the administrator would rely on getting the labor done to improve support and aid. Working with accommodating, obliging, and reassuring is more critical than with someone who is unkind and objective, or inferior, hostile, and uncomfortable (Simmons, 2010).

A compassionate leader aims to reduce the anxiety and obstruction of workers at the workstation. If your work tasks are dangerous, monotonous, and demanding, this approach is operational, but it is not operational. If your work tasks are intrinsically engaging, you do not need to be driven to do the job (Grimsley, 2015).

Enlightened

The organizational environment of the Enlightened has or demonstrates a rational, modern, well-informed, and spiritually conscious perspective (Cayubin, 2012).

Enlightened leadership exercises control over the reasonable use of interest and consideration for an issue. To start, harmonize, and execute strategies to accomplish objectives, people at all levels of the organization have a great autonomy level. Communication is fragile, honest, and free of restrictions. It treats individuals with faith rather than skepticism. Leaders ask for concepts and strive to use recommendations from others. The effects of enlightened leadership are extremely gratifying and efficient. Non-attendance and turnover are minimal, walkouts are non-existent, and competence is high (Manning et al., 2012).

The enlightened atmosphere shows the prospect of the leader's popularity and those who obey the leader. If we understand holiness not as some kind of divine belief or doctrine, but as the domain of consciousness where we practice values such as truth, goodness, magnificence, adoration, and compassion, and also instinct, originality, vision, and absorbed responsiveness, enlightened leadership is mystical. These are the victory components (Goudreau, 2011).

Enlightened leaders encourage their subordinate leaders' talents—building steadily resilient absorption, rather than numbers, on individuals. When people are comfortable with their jobs and their setting, the sought-after upright figures come. Coming to work feels unlimited; at the end of their day, people love the interaction and almost hate going home. Organizational values are useful for a high degree of presentation, harmless and balanced, and generally a good place to function (Herman, 2015).

He added that enlightenment comes when rulers shift to higher expressiveness. Now the brainpower is kicking in—leaders use minds and hearts rather than hands and bravery. They see a future dream and world view—today and tomorrow—and how it can influence business.

With a deep view of the big picture, enlightened leaders become more innovative and inspiring. They offer their people opportunities to do abundant things—for study, growth, and metamorphosis. These leaders share their insights and intuitions with their people to see the big picture. Their followers extend tenacity to their undertakings, making work far more fun.

On several levels and all the way to all characteristics of a society, leadership takes place. The shared perseverance that drives leaders is typically the company or the system's triumph. After explaining governance as a structure, it becomes clear that an understanding of the relationship between leaders and their voters is important. Emerging and retaining effective organizations often requires leaders to understand the organization's history, to be familiar with environmental testing, and to admire the organization's constituents.

The leadership responsibility extends from the executive departments to the public and beyond the local levels. The opportunities and constraints of leaders must be agreed upon for the community to logically support and retain “good leadership.” Many have described the skills and obligations required to be a leader and have spread these skills widely across society.

Essentially, the literature review revealed that management is less about your desires and more about the needs of the individuals and the company you operate. For so many ensembles, leadership styles should not be tried on and see if it works. Still, they should be altered to the particular conditions of the state, the specific needs of the individuals involved, and the actual tests facing the organization. Some climates can arouse the natural motivations of employees. The opposite result in other environments is that workers become depressed and de-motivated about their jobs. Also, the atmosphere is representative of how well the enterprise achieves its full potential. High-performance organizations aim to make full use of the resources of all.

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study model used by the author was was a descriptive survey method.

It was the method suited for the research because the goal of the researcher was to find out the existing leadership style of the school principals in Apopong District as observed and perceived by the respondents at present as autocratic, democratic and laissez-faire; and their school organizational climate as exploitive, impoverished, supportive and enlightened. It supports the idea of Paler-Calmorin and Calmorin (2012) that descriptive survey method is suitable wherever the subjects vary among themselves, and one is interested to know the extent to which different conditions and situations were obtained among these subjects. The word survey signifies the gathering of data regarding the present circumstances. A study is useful in (1) providing the value of facts, and (2) focusing attention on the most important things to be reported.

Research Locale

In the schools of Apopong District, Division of General Santos City, the study was conducted: at Purok 7 New Society, Barangay Apopong both schools are situated, New Society Central Elementary School and GSC Elementary School for the Arts, at Lanton, Barangay Apopong, Lanton Elementary School is located, at Barangay Sinawal located are Lozano Elementary School, Sinawal Elementary School, and Paopao Elementary School. The schools are public institutions under the Department of Education with one district supervisor, six principals and 192 regular permanent teachers for the school year 2014 - 2015.

The researcher used questionnaires in gathering the data in determining the dominant leadership style and organizational climate.

The Leadership Style Questionnaire. This instrument was adapted from the Introduction to Leadership Concepts and Practice by Peter G. Northouse (2014). It consists of 18 questions. The teacher respondents indicated their perception level through a 5-scale rating: Five if they strongly agree, four (4) if they agree, three (3) if moderately agree, two (2) if disagree, and one (1) if they strongly disagree.

It is a self-administered instrument whereby the teacher respondents read the items by themselves.

To be able to identify the leadership style of the principal as observed by the teachers, the following are considered as bases for scoring: The sum of responses on items 1, 4, 7, 10, 13, and 16 refers to authoritarian leadership. The sum of responses on items 2, 5, 8, 11, 14, and 17 refers to democratic oversight, and the sum of responses on items 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, and 18 refers to the laissez-faire leadership style.

After getting the total scores identified per leadership style, the highest total score was considered the dominant leadership style.

The Organizational Climate Questionnaire. From the study of Cayubin (2012), as illustrated by Manning and Curtis (2009), this instrument was adopted. It was a 10-item questionnaire to measure the condition of the school managed by the principal.

It was also a self-administered instrument. The teacher respondents read every item and responded to each item by their own experience and judgment on the school's organizational climate. Every question had a rating of one as the lowest and 20 as the highest.

To identify the school organizational climate, the scores of a and b on each number were added and divided by 2. After separating, the results from 1 to 10 were added and divided by 10.

According to Manning and Curtis (2009), the following interpretation was used to identify the school's organizational climate: Exploitive 1 - 5, Impoverished 6 - 10, Supportive 11 - 15, and Enlightened 16 - 20.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Dominant Leadership Style of School Principals in Apopong District

It shows that the dominant leadership style of school principals in Apopong District as autocratic, democratic or laissez-faire.

Five or 100% of the respondents from Lozano Elementary School observed the leadership style of their principal as democratic, 2 or 67% of the respondents from Sinawal Elementary School observed that their principal's leadership style was autocratic, and 4 or 50% of the respondents from Paopao Elementary School observed it as laissez-faire.

Out of the 130 respondents from Apopong District, 89 or 68% observed the leadership style of their School Principal as democratic.

The democratic leadership style denotes that teachers can be a part of the decision-making process with proper guidance and without pressure. Further, the principals provide their teachers with frequent and supportive communication as well as helping them in finding their "passion."

Moreover, the style of leadership that is participatory is an effective way of convening the school head and the teachers together on problems and decisions to work hand in hand as a team. A participative school administrator takes responsibility for the operation of the school. Still, he shares the operating responsibility with those who perform different tasks by giving them trust and confidence. The teachers feel a sense of involvement in the schools' goals and targets (Bona, 2010).

The democratic style would seem to be the best because of its ability to transform leaders and followers into a cohesive and cooperative group, whose collective performance results in improved quality and quantity of work (Angeles, 2010).

Besides, a leader is not likely to discern everything—this is why somebody hires erudite and practiced people. Using this style is of a common advantage as it permits them to become part of the group and consents an individual to make better judgments (Clark, 2014).

Organizational Climate of Schools in Apopong District

It shows that the organizational climate of schools in Apopong District as experienced by the respondents as exploitive, impoverished, supportive and enlightened.

Out of the 130 respondents of Apopong District, 34 or 65% respondents from New Society Central Elementary School, 28 or 62% respondents from Lanton Elementary School, 13 or 76% respondents from GSC Elementary School for the Arts, 5 or 63% respondents from Paopao Elementary School, 5 or 100% respondents from Lozano Elementary School and 2 or 67% respondents from Sinawal Elementary School experienced a supportive organizational climate.

It infers that teachers' effort and performances are recognized and rewarded positively by the School Principals. Teachers experienced the organization as well organized, with clearly defined goals and responsibilities, having the warmth and support and are innovative and open to new ideas. The dissemination of information in the organization is accurate and available; teamwork is high, and participation in decision making.

It conforms to what Manning et. al., (2012) had stated that a supportive leadership demonstrates a great deal of attention and assurance in members. Authority exists in leaders, but there is a successful conveying of ideas and involvement all through the organization. People apprehend the aims of the organization, and the obligation to achieve them is prevalent. Members feel unrestricted to discourse job-related complications with leaders.

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This leadership design involves wide-ranging member input and contribution to decision-making activities.

Organizational Climate when Analyzed According to Leadership Style of School Principals in Apopong District

It shows that the organizational climate when analyzed according to the leadership style of School Principals in Apopong District.

All schools in Apopong District had a supportive organizational climate though they vary on the leadership style of their Principal. Four out of 6 schools from Apopong District namely New Society Central Elementary School, Lanton Elementary School, GSC Elementary School for the Arts, and Lozano Elementary School had a democratic leadership style, Paopao Elementary School had laissez-faire, and Sinawal Elementary School had an autocratic leadership style.

In a supportive organizational climate, superiors do not basically dispense tasks and then obtain the outcomes. Instead, they work through the responsibilities with employees to develop skills and talent until the leaders do not need to worry about a task done correctly and empowers the subordinates in a particular task (Lacoma, 2014).

According to Rabinowitz (2014), management style depends on the organization's formation of leadership and its management approaches. Reliant on how those fit together, a leader might adopt one of a variety of techniques, each replicated in how the organization maneuvers and how its staff members transmit to one another.

A respectable leader uses all three approaches, depending on what energy it involves between the cohorts, the lead, and the condition (Clark, 2014).

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following are recommended. The principals, like good leaders, must run through all three styles of leadership, depending on what forces are involved and the situation to become successful. They must maintain a supportive organizational climate that offers encouragement or emotional help experienced by the teachers and continue to welcome future researchers who will be conducting studies of significance or relevance to their schools for them to find out their strengths and weaknesses as an administrator and as an organization.

6. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study the following conclusions are drawn. The dominant leadership style of Principals in Apopong District is democratic. The organizational climate of schools in Apopong District is supportive. All schools in Apopong District have a supportive organizational climate though they vary on the leadership style of their principals.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Angeles, E. (2010). Leadership-Key Element In Organizational Management. *The Modern Teacher, Volume 59*, pp. 106-107.
- [2] Apura, V. (2012). *Leadership Styles and Supervisory Styles of School Heads Their Effect to the Performance of Teachers*. Thesis, in Lutayan District I.
- [3] Bautista, G. (2011). What Teachers Usually Expect From Their Boss. *The Modern Teacher, Volume 60 No. 01*, p. 22
- [4] Berman, H. (2015). *Statistics Dictionary. Stat Trek*. Retrieved April 25, 2016 from <http://www.starttrek.com/m/statistics/dictionary.aspx?definition=frequencycount>
- [5] Bona, R. (2010). Participatory Leadership. *The Modern Teacher, Volume 59*, p. 110
- [6] Brennen, A. (2011). Educational and Administration & Supervision, *Articles and Resources on Leadership Styles*
- [7] Calmorin, L. and Calmorin M. (2012). *Research Methods and Thesis Writing Second Edition*. Manila: Rex Book Store, Inc.
- [8] Cayubin, G. (2012). *Organizational Climate, Interpersonal Trust and Attitude Toward Teaching of Secondary Public School Teachers*. Thesis, Graduate School, Mindanao State University, General Santos City.
- [9] Clark, D. (2014). *Leadership Style*. Retrieved February 16, 2015 from <http://www.nwlink.com/~donclark/leader/leadstl.html>.
- [10] Crowther F. (2009). *Developing Teacher Leaders: How Teacher Leadership Enhances School Success Second Edition*. Thousand Oaks, California: Crown Press.
- [11] Da Costa, D. (2012). *The 3 Leadership Styles All Successful Leaders Use*. The Sourcing Institute, Inc.
- [12] Desamito, R. C. (2010). What It Takes To Be A Leader. *The Modern Teacher, Volume 59*, p. 113
- [13] Gibson, J. (2008). *Organization, Behavior, Structure and Process*. Singapore: McGraw Hill
- [14] Grimsley, S. (2015). *Supportive Leadership Style: Definition, Lesson and Quiz*. Retrieved February 27, 2015 from <http://study.com/academy/lesson/supportive-leadership-style-definition-lesson-quiz.html>
- [15] Griffin, R. and Moorhead, G. (2012). *Human Behavior in Organization 2nd Edition*. Singapore: Cengage Learning Asia Pte Ltd.
- [16] Goudreau, J. (2011). *Deepak Chopra On Enlightened Leadership*. Retrieved January 12, 2015 from <http://www.forbes.com/sites/jennagoudreau/2011/01/12/deepak-chopra-on-enlightened-leadership-happiness-meaning-work-employee-engagement-president-barack-obama/>
- [17] Herman, R. (2015). *Enlightened Leaders Make a Difference*. Retrieved February 13, 2015 from http://www.retentionconnection.com/retention_enlightened_leaders.html
- [18] Hoy, W. et al (2013). *Educational Administration: Theory, Research, and Practice Ninth Edition*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- [19] Jones, D. (2015). *Leadership Styles Adapted from “The Wall Street Journal Guide to Management” by Alan Murray*. CA: Dow Jones & Company, Inc.
- [20] Kadian-Baumeyer, K. (2014) *The Blake Mouton Managerial Grid: Five Leadership Styles*. Retrieved October 16, 2014 from <http://study.com/academy/lesson/the-blake-mouton-managerial-grid-five-leadership-styles.html>
- [21] Kendra, C. (2009). *Parenting Styles, The Four Styles of Parenting*. Retrieved October 16, 2014 from <http://www.theardeschool.com/noida/pdf-files/four-style.pdf>
- [22] Lacoma, T. (2014). *Definition of Supportive Leadership Style*, Demand Media. Retrieved October 16, 2014 from <http://smallbusiness.chron.com/definition-supportive-leadership-style-21835.html>

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

 Vol. 10, Issue 3, pp: (63-78), Month: May - June 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

- [23] Mack, S. (2014). *Examples of Leadership Grid Styles*, Demand Media. Retrieved October 25, 2014 from <http://yourbusiness.azcentral.com/examples-leadership-grid-styles-15803.html#>
- [24] Manning, G. and Curtis, K. (2009). *The Art of Leadership 3rd Edition*, New York : McGraw-Hill.
- [25] Manning, G. et al (2012). *Building Community: The Human Side of Work Second Edition*, West Michigan: McGraw-Hill.
- [26] McCarthy, C. (2015). *Leadership Styles*. Retrieved February 13, 2015 from <http://www.boundless.com/management/textbooks/boundless-management-textbook/leadership-9/defining-leadership-68/leadership-styles-343-7980/>
- [27] Northouse, P. (2014). *Introduction to Leadership Concepts and Practices*. Retrieved October 22, 2014, from <http://www.sagepub.com/northouseintro2e>
- [28] Palestini, R. (2011). *Educational Administration 3rd Edition Leading with Mind and Heart*. Maryland: Rowman and Littlefield Publishers, Inc.
- [29] Paster, A. (2013). Teachers' Leadership Styles, Parenting Styles and Attitudes Towards Learning English.
- [30] Pierce, R. (2015). Introduction to Percentages. *Math Is Fun*. Retrieved April 25, 2016 from <http://www.mathisfun.com/percentage.html>
- [31] Rabinowitz P. (2014). *Leadership Styles*. Retrieved February 16, 2015 from <http://ctb.ku.edu/en/table-of-contents/leadership/leadership-ideas/leadership-styles/main>
- [32] Shead, M. (2015). *Examining Leadership*, Leadership 501 . Retrieved January 25, 2015 from <http://www.leadership501.com/leadership-styles/424/>
- [33] Simmons, B. L. (2010). *Nine Supportive Leadership Behaviors*. Retrieved February 14, 2015 from <http://www.bretlsimmons.com/2010-09/nine-supportive-leadership-behaviors/>
- [34] Slocum, P. E. (2009). *Organizational Climate: Application, Assessment, Causes and Consequences*. Thousand Oaks, California: Sage
- [35] Straker, D. (2015). *Likert's Leadership Styles*. Retrieved February 13, 2015 from http://changingminds.org/disciplines/leadership/styles/likert_style.htm.
- [36] Valesky, T. and Owens, R. (2011). *Organizational Behavior in Educational Leadership and School Reform, 10th Edition*. New Jersey: Pearson Education, Inc.
- [37] Woodman, P. (2009). Teller Job Satisfaction and Organization Commitment as They Relate to Career Orientation. Human Relations.

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